

Denitrification in Sunlight and its Retardation.

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In the absence of oxygen and in presence of an easily oxidisable organic substance, many micro-organisms are capable of decomposing nitrates with the evolution of gaseous nitrogen or nitrous oxide or ammonia. This type of denitrification is well known and is one of the first microbiological changes to be investigated.

There is another variety of nitrogen loss, which takes place in presence of oxygen but has not yet been satisfactorily explained. In this paper it will be shown that this loss of nitrogen from the soil is due to an oxidation process followed by a photochemical and catalytic decomposition. This phenomenon of denitrification is of considerable importance as the loss of nitrogen in this process under certain conditions may be double the amount of nitrogen taken up by the plants grown on the soil.

From the researches of Lipman and Blair (*Soil Sci.*, 1921, 12, 1) it appears that nitrogen in the gaseous state is lost from soils when the conditions are favourable for oxidation. The loss amounted to 100 lbs. per acre per year in the first nine inches of the soil and after ten years the loss in New Jersey soil was 1000 lbs. per acre. In California the loss was 500 lbs. per acre in five years. In these experiments the conditions existing in the soil in the past were disturbed by making the soil suitable for more oxidation.

The following figures show the nitrogen loss due to the formation of gaseous nitrogen, in the experiments carried on in the California Experiment Station in the first five years

	Land with crops.	Land without crops.
Loss of nitrogen from 1600 lbs. soil	... 198 g.	124 g.
Nitrogen in crops	... 65	0
Net loss	... 133	124

Similar nitrogen losses have been observed at Rothamsted, (England), and the results are recorded below :—

Treatment.	Crop yield per acre per year.		Recovered crop per year.	N as nitrate in drainage water parts per million.	N in soil.	N lost from soil, per year.
	Grain Bushels.	Straw Cwt.				
NH ₄ salts containing 86 lbs. N + enough P & K salts	26.7	30.75	33.5 lb.	8.5	0.116%	51 lb.
No P or K salts	16.0	14.75	45.0	17.8	0.106	67.5

Loss of nitrogen has been observed by Shutt (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1910, 3, 335) on breaking for cultivation the prairie soil of the Indian Head, Saskatchewan.

Loss of nitrogen in top 8 inches reported by Shutt.

Nitrogen present in unbroken prairie	0.371%	6940 lb. per acre,
„ „ after 22 years' cultivation	0.254%	4750
Loss from soil		2190
Recovered in crop		700
Loss in 22 years		1490
Loss per year		68

Marked loss of nitrogen has also been reported with Minnesota and Kansas soils. Nearly 70% of the added nitrogen is said to have been lost when wheat plots in Rothamsted, England, have received 14 tons of farm-yard manure containing 200 lbs. nitrogen per acre. These losses are more pronounced in soils, which have been highly aerated. From the foregoing observations it can be concluded that nitrogen loss can take place from well aerated soils provided the nitrogen content is high. Moreover, the following results show that this loss is high when the soil is wet and acidic.

Annett, Aiyer and Kayasth (*Mem. Dept. Agric. India, Chemical Series*, 1928, 9, 155) have reported marked losses of nitrogen from a black cotton soil at Nagpur (India) during the heavy August rains, as they did not observe a corresponding gain in the drainage water. Moreover, Meggit (*ibid.*, 1923, 1, 31) has observed great losses of nitrogen in the acid humid soil of Assam (India). Russell ("Soil Conditions and Plant Growth", 1932, pp. 367-69) has stated this problem of the nitrogen loss in the following words :—

"There is considerable difficulty in accounting for the nitrogen lost from the soil during the first 20 or 30 years of cultivation. It has, therefore, been supposed that nitrogen is evolved during the oxidation, and as all attempts to break off nitrogen from nitrate in these conditions have failed, it is assumed to come from the organic matter. This assumption involves the difficulty that no loss of nitrogen has been observed in the straightforward bacterial oxidation of organic substances such as albumin, asparagin or mixtures such as urine or faeces." "Yet somehow and somewhere gaseous nitrogen must be evolved to balance the considerable amount of fixation that is known to take place."

That oxidation of the ammonium salts is an important factor in this type of denitrification is also evident from the following observations. Ni klewski (*Rocz. Nauk. Roln.*, 1923, 9, 1) reported the largest loss of nitrogen as a result of the influence of the nitrifying bacteria on stable manure. When the manure was free from nitrifying bacteria, only 3% nitrogen was lost as ammonia but when supplied with nitrifying bacteria, the manure lost more than 20% of its nitrogen. Moreover, Russell and Richards (*J. Agric. Res.*, 1917, 8, 495) have observed a greater loss of nitrogen when a manure was composted under aerobic than under anaerobic conditions as will be clear from Table I.

TABLE I.

	NH ₃ -N.	NO ₂ -N.	NO ₃ -N.	NH ₂ -N.	Other nitrogenous compounds (proteins).	Total.
Anaerobic conditions.						
Start	28%	0%	0%	8%	64%	100%
At 6° for 50 days	29	0	0	9	57	95
At 26° for 50 days	44	0	0	7	47	98
Aerobic conditions.						
Start	33	0	0	8	59	100
At 15°	11	11	8	0	42	73
At 26°	6	2	7	0	55	69

Recently Viswanath (*Sci. Reports Dept. Agric. Madras*, 1930-31) has obtained greater nitrogen loss and greater velocity of oxidation in the nitrification of ammonium salts than with farm-yard or green manure.

Estimation carried on in different parts of the world especially at Rothamsted (England), Grignon (France) and other places in Europe, Ithaca (U. S. A.), India and Egypt show that the total amount of nitrate present in soils with crop is less than that in neighbouring fallow soils even when correction is applied for the amount of nitrate taken up by the crop. Starkey (*Soil Sci.*, 1927, 27, 319) has also reported that the velocity of nitrate production and evolution of CO_2 is greater in cropped than in fallow land. Table II shows the results obtained by Russell (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1914, 6, 18) regarding the influence of growing plants on the nitrate content of a soil.

TABLE II.

	June, 1911.		July, 1912.	
	Fallow land.	Cropped land.	Fallow land.	Cropped land.
N as nitrate in first 18" of soil ...	54	15	46	13
N in crop per acre ...	...	23	...	6
Total N in lb. per acre ...	54	38	46	19
Deficit in cropped land in lb per acre ...	...	16	...	27
Expressed as nitrogen in parts per million.				
N as nitrate in 0 to 9" depth ...	12	4	8	2
9" to 18" depth ...	9	2	10	9

From quantitative observations on the evolution of carbon dioxide from oxidation reactions taking place in the soil during the growth of plants, Neller (*Soil Sci.*, 1922, 13, 139) concluded that much more rapid oxidation takes place in the soil with growing plants than in the uncropped soils under identical conditions.

Moreover, Burd (*J. Agric. Res.*, 1919, 18, 51) has reported a substantial loss of nitrogen from the aerial parts of the barley plant during the period of translocation of materials in the second stage of the development of the plant.

Martin and Massey (*Wellcome Research Labs., Khartoum Chem. Pub.*, 1923, 29) working at Khartoum (Egypt) reported the disappearance of the nitrates from dry tropical soils.

Recently we have studied the loss of nitrogen when solutions of ammonium salts are exposed to sunlight and air for a long time in open beakers with or without photocatalysts. In order to determine the loss in the dark, similar experiments were carried on in beakers

kept in the dark. The following results showing the ammoniacal nitrite and nitrate nitrogen contents of the exposed and unexposed solutions were obtained when 100 c.c. of 1% (with respect to ammonia) solutions of ammonium salts were exposed to sunlight for 350 hours.

TABLE III.

Amount of NH_3 originally present = 1 g.

„ „ carbonate added = 1 g.

„ „ ZnO or TiO_2 added = 5 gs.

	$(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{SO}_4$ alone.		$(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{SO}_4 + \text{ZnO}$.		$(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{SO}_4 + \text{MgCO}_3 + \text{TiO}_2$.	
	Light.	Dark.	Light.	Dark.	Light.	Dark.
NH_3	0.91	0.980	0.3856	0.460	0.6440	0.6528
NO_2 (Calc. as NH_3)	0.0002	0	0.0005	0.0004	0	0
NO_3 (Calc. as NH_3)	0.0032	0	0.0032	0	0.0035	0
Loss of Nitrogen (Calc. as NH_3)	0.0866	0.020	0.6107	0.5396	0.3525	0.3472
	$\text{NH}_4\text{Cl} + \text{CaCO}_3$		$\text{NH}_4\text{Cl} + \text{CaCO}_3 + \text{TiO}_2$		$\text{NH}_4\text{Cl} + \text{MgCO}_3 + \text{ZnO}$.	
	Light.	Dark.	Light.	Dark.	Light.	Dark.
NH_3	0.6354	0.7100	0.6879	0.6922	0.224	0.3286
NO_2	0.0002	0.0	0.0	0.0001	0.0003	0.0003
NO_3	0.0478	0.0	0.0032	0.0	0.0040	0.0
Loss of N	0.3168	0.2900	0.3089	0.3077	0.7717	0.6711
	$(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{HPO}_4 + \text{TiO}_2$.		$(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{HPO}_4 + \text{CaCO}_3 + \text{TiO}_2$.		$(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{HPO}_4 + \text{MgCO}_3 + \text{TiO}_2$.	
	Light.	Dark.	Light.	Dark.	Light.	Dark.
NH_3	0.5870	0.7054	0.4184	0.6220	0.3768	0.4250
NO_2	0.00025	0.0003	0.0004	0.0003	0.0030	0.0003
NO_3	0.0040	0.0	0.0041	0.0	0.0021	0.0
Loss of N	0.4065	0.2943	0.5771	0.3777	0.6191	0.3744

In these experiments, the open beakers containing the ammonium salt solutions with or without the photocatalysts and carbonate were

exposed to sunlight five days a week for 5 hours a day. After the completion of the experiments, the ammonia, nitrite and nitrate contents of all the solutions were estimated. In the foregoing tables, in order to obtain comparable results, the nitrite and nitrate contents of the solutions have been expressed in terms of ammonia.

The foregoing results show that the loss of nitrogen on exposing ammonium salt solutions to light and air is always greater in light than in the dark. In presence of zinc oxide and magnesium carbonate the loss is greater than with calcium carbonate, because more of free ammonia escapes due to the greater alkalinity of the medium containing zinc oxide or magnesium carbonate. The loss of nitrogen from all these solutions cannot be due only to the escape of ammonia from the solutions due to the alkalinity of the medium. The solutions in the beakers containing the ammonium sulphate alone and ammonium phosphate and TiO_2 were distinctly acidic from the beginning and hence in these beakers there was no appreciable loss of nitrogen as ammonia. Moreover, the beakers containing ammonium chloride and calcium carbonate showed alkaline reaction in the beginning and acidic reaction after the end of the exposure, whilst the solutions in the beakers kept in the dark were alkaline throughout. Similar results showing increased acidity after exposure were observed with the other reaction mixtures. These results show that a part of the ammonium ion was replaced by the acidic nitrite and nitrate ions on exposure to light due to the photo-oxidation of the ammonium salts. A part of the ammonium nitrite produced in this way seems to be decomposed into nitrogen and water and that is why in all beakers even in the ones containing acidic solutions from the very beginning, there is greater loss of nitrogen in the exposed than in the unexposed solutions.

In order to throw further light on this problem, we have carried several experiments by exposing solutions of ammonium chloride mixed with sodium nitrite of different concentrations in presence of TiO_2 , Fe_2O_3 , ZnO , sterilised and unsterilised soils. The total volume of the solutions was made up to 50 c.c. and exposed to sunlight in open beakers for about 7 hours every day. After the necessary exposure to light, the ammoniacal nitrogen, nitrite nitrogen and the nitrate nitrogen of the solutions were estimated. In some of the experiments the influence of the addition of cane sugar has also been investigated. The results obtained with sterilised and unsterilised soils are recorded in the following tables.

TABLE IV.

Exposure to sunlight from 7th October to 20th November, 1934. Total exposure=77 hours.

	N added as NH ₃	N added as nitrite.	Total N added.	Ammoniacal N left	NO ₂ -N left.	NO ₃ -N formed.	N lost.	N lost.
10 g. unsterilised soil	0.14 g.	0.0198 g.	0.1598 g.	0.0933 g.	0.06912 g.	0.00019 g.	0.0513 g.	39.3
" sterilised	0.14	0.0138	0.1538	0.0789	0.00712	0.00058	0.673	43.6
" unsterilised + 0.3 g. cane sugar	0.14	0.0138	0.1538	0.0986	0.011	0.00001	0.0442	28.6
" sterilised + 0.3 g. cane sugar	0.14	0.0198	0.1598	0.0920	0.0081	0.00002	0.0537	34.9
" unsterilised + 1 g. cane sugar	0.14	0.0198	0.1598	0.103	0.011	0	0.0998	25.7
" sterilised + 1 g. cane sugar	0.14	0.0198	0.1598	0.090	0.0092	0	0.0546	35.6
" unsterilised + 0.1 g. cane sugar	0.14	0.0514	0.1914	0.070	0.0321	0.00071	0.0886	46.3
" sterilised + 0.1 g. cane sugar	0.14	0.0514	0.1914	0.063	0.0292	0.00092	0.0983	51.6
" unsterilised + 0.1 g. cane sugar	0.14	0.0514	0.1914	0.0501	0.0438	0.00002	0.0678	50.1
" sterilised + 0.3 g. cane sugar	0.14	0.0514	0.1914	0.080	0.0422	0.00008	0.0691	56.1
" unsterilised + 0.3 g. cane sugar	0.14	0.0514	0.1914	0.0812	0.0441	0	0.0661	34.5
" sterilised + 1 g. cane sugar	0.14	0.0514	0.1914	0.080	0.0412	0	0.0702	36.6
" sterilised + 1 g. cane sugar + 1 c. cane sugar	0.14	0.138	0.278	0.0375	0.0521	0.0021	0.1863	67.0
10 g. unsterilised + 0.3 g. cane sugar	0.14	0.138	0.278	0.0388	0.0460	0.0092	0.1930	69.4
" sterilised + 0.3 g. cane sugar	0.14	0.138	0.278	0.0421	0.0981	0.00003	0.1869	49.6
" unsterilised + 0.3 g. cane sugar	0.14	0.138	0.278	0.0873	0.0589	0.00012	0.1848	66.4
" sterilised + 0.3 g. cane sugar	0.14	0.138	0.278	0.0468	0.0992	0	0.139	47.8
" unsterilised + 1 g. cane sugar	0.14	0.138	0.278	0.0412	0.0592	0	0.1784	64.1
" sterilised + 1 g. cane sugar	0.14	0.138	0.278	0.0412	0.0592	0	0.1784	64.1

TABLE V.

Exposure to sunlight from 30th July to 5th September, 1934. Total exposure = 72 hours.

	N added as ammonia.	N added as nitrite.	Total N added.	Ammoniacal N left.	NO ₂ -N left.	NO ₃ -N formed.	N lost.	N. lost.
1 g. sterilised soil	0.014 g.	0.014 g.	0.028 g.	0 g.	0.00049 g.	0.00063 g.	0.0223 g.	79%
" unsterilised "	0.014	0.014	0.028	0	0.00062	0.0027	0.0255	80
2 g. sterilised "	0.028	0.028	0.056	0	0.00125	0.00056	0.050	89
" unsterilised "	0.028	0.028	0.056	0	0.00145	0.00376	0.052	93
4 g. sterilised "	0.056	0.056	0.112	0	0.00464	0.0085	0.104	92
" unsterilised "	0.056	0.056	0.112	0	0.00488	0.0026	0.106	98
8 g. sterilised "	0.112	0.112	0.224	0.000386	0.00866	0.008	0.211	94
" unsterilised "	0.112	0.112	0.224	0.000312	0.00689	0.0073	0.210	94

TABLE VI.

Exposure to sunlight from 10th September to 5th October, 1934. Total exposure = 64 hours.

30 g. unsterilised soil	0.42 g.	0.42 g.	0.84 g.	0.138 g.	0.056 g.	0.017 g.	0.69 g.	76%
" " + 5 g. cane sugar	0.42	0.42	0.84	0.200	0.411	0	0.229	27
" unsterilised soil	0.42	0.315	0.735	0.155	0.0825	0.005	0.425	74
" " + 5 g. cane sugar	0.42	0.315	0.735	0.165	0.269	0	0.281	80

The foregoing results show that in all the solutions, there is a marked loss of nitrogen on exposure to sunlight due to the decomposition of ammonium nitrite. It is of great interest to note that the loss is less marked with dilute solutions of ammonium nitrite than in the stronger solutions when the weight of the soil is the same and the addition of cane sugar considerably retards this nitrogen loss and nitrate formation. Moreover, the results show that the decomposition of ammonium nitrite is greater, the greater the intensity of the light, the loss is greater in August and September than in October and November.

These observations on nitrogen loss in presence of air recorded in the foregoing pages which are unaccountable from the bacterial viewpoint (*vide* Russell's quotation on page 69) are explained from the following considerations.

The soil invariably contains some ammonium salts mainly as a result of the oxidation of the amino acids set free from its proteins. By the process of nitrification caused by light or bacteria the ammonium salts are first oxidised to nitrite. In other words, ammonium nitrite may be produced in the soil when a supply of air and light or nitrifying bacteria are available. Some years ago Dhar (*Proc. K. Akad. Wetensch. Amsterdam*, 1920, 23, 309) observed that solutions of ammonium nitrite decompose into nitrogen and water when exposed to sunlight and this photochemical decomposition is facilitated by acids and different solid surfaces. Our experiments by exposing solutions of ammonium salts and sodium nitrite to sunlight mixed with sterilised soil or unsterilised soil recorded in Tables IV, V and VI show marked decomposition of the ammonium nitrite in light. In presence of TiO_2 , ZnO , Fe_2O_3 , etc., the photo-decomposition of ammonium nitrite has also been observed. In several of these experiments specially in the stronger solutions and in the absence of sugar, copious evolution of gaseous nitrogen has been noted. Similar decomposition of ammonium nitrite formed temporarily in the soil from the processes of ammonification and nitrification is likely to take place in nature specially in humid soils. This decomposition of ammonium nitrite in the soil will be more evident when virgin or prairie soils are ploughed for cultivation. The organic nitrogenous compounds present in the soil have a chance to be oxidised first to ammonia and then to nitrite and finally to nitrate by the increase of aeration effected by ploughing. It seems that in the soil, normally the processes of ammonification and nitrification can go on simul-

taneously and thus at a certain stage in the processes of oxidation, ammonium nitrite may be generated and this being an unstable substance specially in presence of light and the soil surface acting as a catalyst, will partially decompose with the liberation of gaseous nitrogen. Moreover, when the nitrogenous manure is in large amounts and there is sufficient aeration, the possibility of the formation of the easily decomposable ammonium nitrite is increased and there is partial decomposition of this substance from soils receiving large amounts of farm-yard manures or ammonium salts. For the production of ammonium nitrite in the soil, aeration is necessary and that is why Russell and Richards observed more marked loss of nitrogen in aerobic than in anaerobic conditions in composting as already reported. In tropical countries the decomposition of ammonium nitrite formed in the soil is likely to be marked because of the high temperature and strong sunlight; like sunlight, high temperature also facilitates the decomposition of ammonium nitrite.

The observation of Niklewski (*loc. cit.*) that there is more loss of nitrogen from stable manure in presence of nitrifying bacteria than in their absence, is also clear from the foregoing lines. As bacterial nitrification is an oxidation phenomenon, the ammonium salts in the manure are to a larger extent oxidised to nitrite when nitrifying bacteria are added to the manure than in their absence. Hence in the presence of the nitrifying bacteria, there is the possibility of the formation and decomposition of larger amounts of ammonium nitrite than in the absence of the bacteria. The observations of Viswanath showing greater oxidation and greater nitrogen loss with ammonium salts on nitrification than with farm-yard and green manures, can be easily understood from the view point advanced in this paper. As these experiments were carried on under field conditions, the photochemical and catalytic decomposition of a part of the ammonium nitrite and nitrous acid formed was possible.

It has been already stated that in cropped soils there is more nitrogen loss than in uncropped soils under the same conditions. This is due to the fact that there is more oxidation taking place in soils with growing crops than in fallow lands. This behaviour has been observed in different stations all over the world and is explicable from the view point of the partial decomposition of ammonium nitrite produced in the soil even for a short time. In the process of nitrification, the basic ammonium ion is replaced first by the acidic nitrite ion and finally by the nitrate ion and hence the acidity of the

soil undergoing nitrification is increased. Moreover, it has been already stated that the decomposition of ammonium nitrite is facilitated by acids and hence in soils not containing calcium carbonate, the loss of nitrogen in this manner will be marked.

It is well known that the soil-nitrogen cannot be increased alone without a corresponding increase in its carbon content. This leads to the interesting conclusion that in presence of carbonaceous matter, the soil-nitrogen is protected, because the carbonaceous matter acts as a negative catalyst and retards the process of nitrification which is an oxidation reaction. Unless nitrification takes place and nitrite ion is formed in place of ammonium ion, the formation and decomposition of ammonium nitrite are not possible. Hence in presence of large amounts of carbonaceous matter, this type of loss of nitrogen, would not be pronounced. Our experiments recorded in Tables IV and VI show that the addition of cane sugar markedly decreases the nitrate formation and loss of nitrogen from solutions containing ammonium and nitrite ions. On the other hand, in the absence of carbonaceous matter, the soil nitrogenous compounds will undergo oxidation more readily than in the presence of carbonaceous substances with the formation of ammonium nitrite, which is liable to be partially decomposed in the soil with consequent loss of nitrogen. From this point of view, the observations of Viswanath that there is greater oxidation and loss of nitrogen when ammonium salts are allowed to nitrify than with farm yard and green manures are easily explained. In the latter group of manures, along with nitrogenous compounds, there are carbonaceous compounds like cellulose, carbohydrates, fats, etc., which acting as negative catalysts markedly retard the oxidation of the proteins, amino acids and ammonium salts to nitrite and nitrate and hence in presence of cellulose, carbohydrates, fats, etc., added with farm yard and green manures, there is less oxidation of ammonium salts to nitrite and hence less chance for the formation and decomposition of ammonium nitrite. In several publications from these laboratories (*cf.* Dhar "New Conceptions in Biochemistry, 1932 pp. 44-45), it has been shown that both carbohydrate and fats markedly act as negative catalysts and retard the oxidation of amino acids and proteins and that is why carbohydrates and fats act as protein sparer in the animal body. Similarly in the soil, carbonaceous substances like cellulose, carbohydrates, fats, etc., added with organic manures retard the oxidation of proteins, amino acids, and ammonium salts by air and thus act as protectors

of the soil nitrogen compounds. It is clear, therefore, that when the carbon content of a soil is high and the nitrogen content low, there will be less oxidation of the soil nitrogen and less chance for the formation and decomposition of ammonium nitrite and less nitrogen loss than when the carbon content is low and nitrogen content high. The foregoing observations justify the application of organic manures for preserving the nitrogen of soils, specially in tropical countries, where due to sunlight and high temperature, the velocity of the oxidation of the soil organic and inorganic compounds is high and the nitrogenous compounds want more protection than in temperate climates.

Molasses from sugar factories in India are practically wasted now. They should be added to the soil for the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen as has been observed by us and for the preservation of the soil nitrogen compounds by decreasing their too rapid oxidation. Of course too little oxidation of the protein present in the soil by the addition of molasses will not make the soil suitable for the growth of crops. It seems necessary that an equilibrium should be established between the oxidised and the unoxidised proteins, ammonium salts and other nitrogenous compounds, which are present in the soil for maintaining its fertility at a proper level. Too much oxidation of the nitrogenous substances and ammonium salts may entail marked nitrogen loss by this type of denitrification, and too little oxidation will not make the soil fertile enough for a good yield of crop. Hence the molasses should not be added in very large amounts and after the addition of molasses, the soil should be ploughed several times to help oxidation. In our field experiments at Allahabad, we have observed that the ammonia content of a garden soil is increased ten times by the addition of molasses in the ratio one part of molasses in 100 parts of soil and the soil is well aerated. If the soil is properly aerated by ploughing, molasses added in moderate amounts should prove to be a valuable fertiliser, specially in tropical countries. Moreover, the observation of Lipman and Blair (*loc cit.*) that nitrogen is lost from cropped soils inspite of added nitrogenous fertilisers is explained, because of the absence of the requisite amount of carbonaceous substances for the preservation of the nitrogenous compounds of the soil, the soil nitrogenous compounds are oxidised too rapidly forming ammonium nitrite (*cf.* Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 883).

The experiments carried on in presence of cane sugar show that

the loss of nitrogen in the solutions containing sugar is much less than in the other beakers without sugar. The greater the sugar added, the greater is the retardation of the decomposition. Both the ammoniacal and nitrite nitrogen remaining in the beakers after exposure are greater in the presence of sugar than in its absence and this behaviour is more marked with the unsterilised than with the sterilised soils. It seems that in presence of sugar along with the retardation of the decomposition of ammonium nitrite, nitrogen fixation may take place and thus the apparent loss of nitrogen is less. We have observed nitrogen fixation as ammonia increment in soils when exposed to light in presence of cane sugar. Further work on the decomposition of dilute solutions of ammonium nitrite and the influence of sugars on this decomposition and nitrogen fixation is in progress.

From our experiments we find that the decomposition of ammonium nitrite is easy when a moderately strong solution containing ammonium and nitrite ions are exposed to light and this decomposition is favoured by acids. Our results recorded in Table IV, show that the nitrogen loss is less in dilute solutions than in strong solutions. It seems that Barritt (*Biochem. J.*, 1931, 25, 1965) did not observe the decomposition of ammonium nitrite, because his solution was not exposed to light and was dilute and the temperature of the solution low. A mixture of an ammonium salt and a nitrite in the solid state does not decompose appreciably in sunlight. In the soil under ordinary conditions, when unmanured, this decomposition is not much, because the soil is dry and the amount of ammonia being usually small, the quantity of ammonium nitrite formed is still smaller, and its decomposition is not expected to be high. Under normal circumstances, this type of denitrification should be observed more readily when large amounts of nitrogenous compounds are added to the soil or new soils are broken up for cultivation specially in warm and humid climates but when the soil nitrogen is small due to repeated cultivation without any addition of manure, this loss is likely to be slight.

In the experiments of Dhar, Bhattacharyya, and Biswas (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 699) on the photonitrification of ammonium salts, the soil was kept very dry most of the time and the amount of ammoniacal nitrogen added was small, hence the possibility of the decomposition of the ammonium nitrite formed by oxidation of the ammonium salt was not high. The nitrite is also oxidised to nitrate, which is stable in light.

Under certain circumstances, the soil nitrate may be reduced to nitrite by the organic substances in the soil possibly with the simultaneous formation of organic acids. In this way there is also the possibility of the generation of ammonium nitrite and nitrous acid and their decomposition and consequent loss of nitrogen. The formation of nitrite from nitrate has been suspected by Nagaoka (*Bull. Coll. Agric. Tokyo*, 1904, 6, No. 3, 285), Daikubara and Imaseki (*Bull. Imp. Centr. Agric. Expt. Sta. Japan*, 1907, 1, No. 2, 7), in the Japanese swampy rice fields, by Keley (*Hawaii Agric. Exp. Sta. Bull.* 1911, 24) in Hawaii and by Sen (*Proc. Imp. Council Agric. Res.*, 1933) in Bengal (India). It is well known that there are numerous micro-organisms in the soil capable of reducing nitrate to nitrite in presence of reducing substances like peptone, glucose, glycerol, carbohydrates. Many aerobic micro-organisms can act anaerobically in the presence of nitrate.

Moreover, partial loss of nitrogen from the soil is possible from the decomposition of nitrous acid according to the equation,

The nitrite formed either by the oxidation of ammonia or by the reduction of nitrate may be easily converted into nitrous acid by the acids, which may be present in the soil because nitrous acid is a comparatively weak acid (dissociation constant = 4×10^{-4}). Even carbonic acid slowly decomposes nitrites, as nitrous acid itself is unstable and decomposes into nitric acid and nitric oxide, which may escape in the gaseous condition. It seems that the decompositions of ammonium nitrite and nitrous acid will be more pronounced in solutions than in dry soil and thus the observations of Meggitt (*Mem. Dept. Agric. India*, 1923, 7, 31) on great losses of nitrogen in the acid humid soil in Assam (India) may be explained. There is also the possibility of the reaction of nitrous acid on amines, amides, and amino acids which may sometimes be formed in the decomposition of soil organic substances.

SUMMARY.

1. The researches of different investigators show that nitrogen in the gaseous state is lost from soils when the conditions are favourable for oxidation. The loss of nitrogen in this process may be double the amount of nitrogen taken up by the plants grown on the soil.

2. A greater loss of nitrogen is observed when a manure is composted under aerobic than anaerobic conditions. Moreover, when there is a large amount of carbonaceous matter present in the manures along with nitrogenous compounds, the velocity of the oxidation of nitrogenous compounds and the amount of nitrogen loss are also decreased.

3. Experiments carried on at different places show that the total amount of nitrate present in soils containing crops is less than that in neighbouring fallow soils even when a correction is applied for the amount of nitrate taken up by the crop. The oxidation processes are more vigorous in soils with crops than in those without them.

4. Our experimental results show that the loss of nitrogen on exposing ammonium salt solutions to light and air is always greater in light than in the dark. Moreover, solutions of ammonium chloride and sodium nitrite decompose readily with evolution of nitrogen when exposed to sunlight in open beakers mixed with sterilised and unsterilised soils. This decomposition is considerably less in dilute solutions of ammonium nitrite and also when cane sugar is added to the solutions containing ammonium and nitrite ions.

5. All these observations have been explained from the view point that in the processes of ammonification, and nitrification taking place in the soil or in solutions, ammonium nitrite is produced. Ammonium nitrite has been found to be decomposed into nitrogen and water readily by increase of temperature or exposing it to light. The formation of ammonium nitrite from ammonium salts or proteins requires oxygen and that is why, this type of denitrification is facilitated by increased soil aeration and also soil acidity, as nitrous acid also undergoes decomposition.

6. Addition of carbonaceous substances like molasses tends to preserve the soil nitrogen by decreasing the velocity of the oxidation of the nitrogenous compounds present in the soil and thus decreasing the probability of the formation and decomposition of ammonium nitrite. Moreover, molasses, when added to soil in moderate amounts and the soil is properly aerated for helping the oxidation reactions, cause nitrogen fixation as evidenced by the increase of ammoniacal nitrogen of soil.

The method was to determine the amount of hydrolysis in certain periods produced by a definite weight of the enzyme in a substrate (like peptone) and to compare this with the amount of hydrolysis produced by the same weight of the enzyme after the latter had been exposed to the action of a dyestuff at a concentration of 1/2000 or of a narcotic at a concentration of 1/4000 for an hour. The concentration of the dyestuff was 1/5000 and of the narcotic 1/10,000 in the reaction vessel.

The action of a large number of acidic and basic representative dyestuffs from different series has been tried. The names of the dyes are given in the relevant tables.

The Inhibiting Action of Dyestuffs on Trypsin.

The enzyme material was a preparation of pancreatic trypsin by Messrs. Carnick & Co., U.S.A., that is known by the name of "Trypsogen". Cystin, neutralised and brought up to the desired p_H , was used throughout as an activator (*cf.* Grassman, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1930, 186, 183). Phosphate buffer (p_H 8.67) was used in these experiments.

0.2 G. of trypsin dissolved in water and 0.06 g. of cystin dissolved in a minimum quantity of NaOH solution and brought to the desired p_H (8.67) with HCl solution were transferred to a 25 c.c. measuring flask. 2 C.c. of phosphate buffer of p_H 8.67 and 2 c.c. of the dye solution were also added to the flask. The concentration of the dyestuff in the flask was now 1/2000. The measuring flask was then allowed to stay for an hour in a thermostat at a temperature of 37° so that the enzyme was subjected to the action of dyestuff. After this period 5 c.c. of a peptone solution that was previously brought up to p_H 8.67 were added quickly to the measuring flask and the volume made up to 25 c.c. with water. The concentration of the dyestuff was now 1/5000. 4% Solution of the peptone was used. This peptone solution and water were also kept in the thermostat to acquire the same temperature as the solution, *i.e.*, 37°. Now 2 c.c. of the solution were withdrawn from the flask and allowed to run into the reaction chamber of a micro-Van Slyke apparatus and the NH_2 -nitrogen determination made in the usual way (Van Slyke, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1915, 23, 407). The volume of the nitrogen in the burette was noted. The measuring flask with the solution was kept in the thermostat at the same temperature and a second Van Slyke

determination with 2 c.c. was made after 30 minutes of the first determination. A third determination was made after an hour.

Blank experiment was done without the dyestuff and this blank determination was made from time to time in order to see that the activity of the enzyme remained practically identical and also to take into account the slight changes in activity from time to time. The results obtained are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I.

*Percentage inhibition of hgdrolysis of peptone with trypsin
by different dyestuffs.*

$p_H = 8.67$. Temp. = 37° .

Basic dyestuffs (1/2000).	% Inhibition.	Basic dyestuffs (1/2000).	% Inhibition.
Brilliant green	18	Toluidine blue	35
Malachite green	0	Janus green	6
Methyl violet	19	Neutral red	0
Crystal violet	0	Chrysoidin	26
Ethyl violet	20	Pyronine	19
Gentian violet	0	Methylene violet	22
Bismarck brown.	16	Safranine	0
Methylene blue	0	Auramine	28
Acid dyestuffs (1/2000).	% Inhibition.	Acid dyestuff (1/2000).	% Inhibition.
Erythrosin	26	Soluble blue	16
Eosin yellow	29	Congo red	33
Eosin bluish	28	Benzopurputin	0
Acid green	20	Orange G.	6
Acid fuchsin	36	Cyanin chloride	11
Water blue	9	Haemotoxylin	30

Conclusion.—It would appear from above that some basic and all acidic dyestuffs are toxic to trypsin at p_H 8.67 and at a concentration of 1/2000. It must be observed, however, that the inhibition never exceeds 36% and in no case reaches 100% that was observed

in the case of the dehydrogenase, fumarase and urease studied by Quastel. It is reasonable to suppose that the inhibiting action of dyestuffs is due to their combination with the enzyme and the enzyme trypsin, therefore, must possess both acidic and basic groups and have amphoteric properties. In this, trypsin resembles fumarase on which both acidic and basic dyestuffs exert toxic action and differs from dehydrogenase and urease whose action is inhibited by basic dyestuffs alone (Quastel. *loc. cit.*).

There is, however, a marked specificity in action both among the acidic and basic dyestuffs and dyestuffs belonging to the same series act in quite different ways. Thus of the basic dyestuffs of the triphenylmethane series, malachite green, crystal violet and gentian violet exert no toxic action, while brilliant green, methyl violet, and ethyl violet inhibit almost to the same extent. The acid dyestuffs of the triphenylmethane series (acid green, acid fuchsin, water blue, soluble blue) are all toxic. Methylene blue is inert while toluidine blue exerts the highest toxic action amongst the basic dyestuffs. Safranin is, as was found by Marston, inert but methylene violet is toxic. Similar behaviour was also observed by Quastel in his investigations, who found, for instance, neutral red inert but Janus green toxic, orange G. inert but congo red highly toxic towards fumarase.

It will thus be seen that the *structure* of the dyestuff molecule is also an important factor in determining its toxic action.

Dyestuffs and Proteolytic Action of Papain.

Papain differs from trypsin in having a pH optimum (pH 5.0) quite different from that of trypsin. The action of all the above dyestuffs was tried on papain. Experiments were done both with Merck's papain (*Succus caricae Papayae Siccatus*) and also with a sample of papain prepared by us from the fresh milky juice of the carica papaya. This was done by extracting the dried juice with water, centrifuging and precipitating the clear liquid with alcohol. The precipitate was freed from alcohol and was found to be about three times more active than the Merck's preparation.

The activation of the enzyme was affected by cystein, cystin being inert in this case (*vide*, Grassmann, *loc. cit.*). The reaction was carried at pH 5.0. Gelatine was used as the substrate.

0.2 G. of Merck's papain was taken. A 0.1M solution of cystein was prepared and 1 c.c. of the solution was added to the papain solu-

tion for activation. Citrate buffer ($p_H 5.0$) was used. The cystein solution was brought to the same p_H by adding alkali solution in drops. The solution of papain, cystein (1 c.c.) and the dyestuff (2 c.c.) were taken in a 25 c.c. measuring flask and the mixture was allowed to remain for an hour in the thermostat at 37° . The concentration of the dyestuff was 1/2000. Just before the reaction, 10 c.c. of a 3% gelatine solution at $p_H 5.0$ was added to the measuring flask and the volume was made up to 25 c.c. with water, the temperature of water and gelatine being also 37° . The concentration of the dyestuff was now 1/5000, 2 c.c. of the mixture were withdrawn and analysed in the Van Slyke apparatus. A second determination was made after an hour of the first reaction. The final determination was made after 2 hours. In the case of laboratory prepared papain 0.08 g. was taken in each reaction. The results obtained are summarised in Table II.

TABLE II.

Percentage inhibition by dyestuffs of gelatine hydrolysis by papain.

$p_H = 5.0$. Temp. = 37° .

Basic dyestuff. (1/2000)	% Inhibition		Basic dyestuff. (1/2000)	% Inhibition	
	Merck's papain.	Prepared papain.		Merck's papain.	Prepared papain.
Brilliant green	5	6	Toluidine blue	6	4
Malachite green	1	3	Janus green	17	5
Methyl violet	4	4	Neutral red	4	2
Ethyl violet	11	2	Chrysoidin	25	9
Gentian violet	1	6	Pyronin	3	2
Bismarck brown	3	4	Methylene violet	9	4
Methylene blue	6	3	Safranin	1	3
			Auramin (1/2000)	6	2
Erythrosin	26	16	Soluble blue	9	6
Eosin yellow	5	3	Congo red	18	1
Eosine bluish	13	6	Benzopurpurin	13	12
Acid green	1	6	Crystal scarlet	5	16
Acid fuchsin	5	9	Orange G.	12	2
Water blue	2	4	Cyanin chloride	12	6
			Haematoxylin	7	6

The above table makes it clear that as in the case of trypsin both acidic and basic dyestuffs are toxic showing the amphoteric nature of papain. The same specificity of action amongst dyestuffs of the same series is to be observed here. Thus Janus green is fairly toxic while neutral red is inert. Here again the importance of the structure of a dyestuff in determining its toxic action is apparent.

One fact, however, forces itself upon our observation. The dyestuffs appear to be less toxic towards the purer laboratory preparation of papain than towards the less active and therefore, less pure Merck's papain. Similar observations have been made by Quastel (*Biochem. J.*, 1932, 26, 1683) in his study of the action of dyestuffs on urease. It is possible that some substance is present in Merck's preparation, which enhances the toxicity of the dyestuffs.

Crystal scarlet alone is more toxic towards the purer preparation. Quastel also found neutral red and Janus green more toxic towards the purer urease.

*The Action of Narcotics on the Proteolytic Enzymes,
Trypsin and Papain.*

Although there are some observations on the effect of narcotics on the Schardinger enzyme and succinic dehydrogenase by Sen (*Biochem. J.*, 1931, 25, 849) and on brain dehydrogenase by Quastel (*ibid.*, 1932, 26, 1672) no data are available on the action of narcotics on proteolytic enzymes. The inhibiting effect of narcotics on enzymic reactions is supposed to be due to the preferential adsorption of these substances on enzyme surfaces and the reaction velocity is diminished owing to the displacement of the substrates from the enzyme surface by the narcotics (Warburg, *Biochem. Z.*, 1921, 119, 134).

The action of the narcotics, diethylurea, ethyl urethane, phenyl urethane, vanillin and also of the following substances, catechol, pyrogallol, gallic acid and sodium hydrosulphite on trypsin and papain has been tried in order to find out if it might throw some light on the nature of the enzymes.

Carrick's "Trypsogen" and papain prepared in the laboratory by us were employed. The same procedure was employed as in the case of the dyestuffs with the difference that the solution of the dyestuff was replaced by the same volume of a solution of the narcotic. The enzyme in presence of the activator was subjected to the action of the narcotic

at a concentration of 1/4000 for an hour and when finally the substrate solution was added and the reaction mixture was made up to 25 c.c., the concentration of the narcotic fell to 1/10,000. The results are as follows.

TABLE III.

Percentage inhibition by narcotics of peptone hydrolysis by trypsin.

$p_H=8.67$. Temp. = 37°

Narcotic ($\frac{1}{4000}$)	Percentage inhibition after	
	36 min.	65 min.
Pyrogallol	2	9
Ethyl urethane	0	3
Diethylurea	0	9
Vanillin	6	7
Gallic acid	0	10
Catechol	0	10
Phenyl urethane	0	0
Sodium hydrosulphite	0	7

TABLE IV.

Percentage inhibition by narcotics of gelatine hydrolysis by papain.

$p_H=5$. Temp. = 37° .

Narcotic ($\frac{1}{4000}$)	Percentage inhibition after	
	60 min.	120 min.
Pyrogallol	0	0
Ethyl urethane	5	5
Diethyl urea	0	0
Vanillin	0	9
Gallic acid	5	16
Catechol	0	0
Phenyl urethane	3	3
Sodium hydrosulphite	0	0

It will be observed that in the case of papain the narcotics are without any action, only gallic acid, vanillin and ethyl urethane causing some inhibition. The inhibiting action increases with time. In the case of trypsin practically all the substances tried show no effect for the first hour of the reaction but an appreciable inhibiting action is to be noticed after two hours. This shows that the adsorption of the narcotics on trypsin surface is very slow and is inappreciable for the first two hours. Similar results were obtained by Quastel in the case of the action of Somnifaine on brain dehydrogenase.

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